

Supplementary Material : Exploring Transcript Isoorthology Using Large Language Model Embeddings

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S1-Table1 : Overview of the 500 gene families: gene, transcript, and homology counts

	# families	#Genes			#Transcripts		
		Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg
Dataset	500	5	134	6,792	5	229	18,22

	# pairs			#Orthologous pairs			#Paralogous pairs		
	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg
Dataset	10	8911	41,86	0	413	9,386	0	8498	32,474

S1-Table2 : Prediction summary

Table 1: Method: kmeans+euclidean - Confusion-matrix summary by homology type

Homology type	Agree	Extra	Missing	Ref	Pred	Total Pred
ortho-isoorthologs	2322	1520	6582	8904	3842	47297
ortho-orthologs	3163	9091	5741	8904	12254	
para-isoorthologs	5307	4733	8131	13438	10040	
para-orthologs	6038	16655	7400	13438	22693	
recent-paralogs	2496	9854	180	2676	12350	

Table 2: Method: kmedoids+cosine - Confusion-matrix summary by homology type

Homology type	Agree	Extra	Missing	Ref	Pred	Total Pred
ortho-isoorthologs	2438	1489	6466	8904	3927	51235
ortho-orthologs	3347	9878	5557	8904	13225	
para-isoorthologs	5302	4799	8136	13438	10101	
para-orthologs	6096	18488	7342	13438	24584	
recent-paralogs	2514	10912	162	2676	13426	

Table 3: Method: kmedoids+euclidean - Confusion-matrix summary by homology type

Homology type	Agree	Extra	Missing	Ref	Pred	Total Pred
ortho-isoorthologs	2511	1356	6393	8904	3867	48145
ortho-orthologs	3320	8678	5584	8904	11998	
para-isoorthologs	5391	4917	8047	13438	10308	
para-orthologs	6098	16958	7340	13438	23056	
recent-paralogs	2501	10590	175	2676	13091	

S1-Figure1 : Comparative Analysis of Homology Prediction Accuracy

Figure 1: Venn diagram matrix illustrating the overlap between predicted (our alignment-free approaches) and reference (*tsm – method*) homology sets. The matrix compares three clustering strategies (Rows: k-means with Euclidean distance, k-medoids with Cosine similarity, and k-medoids with Euclidean distance) across five distinct homology types (Columns). In each diagram, the colored circle represents the Reference set (Ground Truth), while the gray dashed circle represents the Predicted set generated by the method. The intersection area corresponds to the number of correctly identified relationships (Agree). The relative sizes of the non-overlapping regions visually demonstrate False Negatives (Missing) and False Positives (Extra). Precision and Recall metrics are provided below each diagram to quantify the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity.

S1-Figure2 : Side-by-side comparison of Yang-Clark functional similarity distributions

(a) k-medoids+cosine: Biological Process

(b) tsm-method: Biological Process

(c) k-medoids+cosine: Cellular Component

(d) tsm-method: Cellular Component

(e) k-medoids+cosine: Molecular Function

(f) tsm-method: Molecular Function

Figure 2: Side-by-side comparison of Yang-Clark functional similarity distributions. The left column displays results from our proposed alignment-free framework (*k-medoids + Cosine*), while the right column shows the alignment-based *tsm-method*. Rows correspond to Biological Process (top), Cellular Component (middle), and Molecular Function (bottom). This arrangement highlights the high concordance between the two methods, particularly in the Molecular Function aspect.

S1-Figure3 : Distribution of silhouette scores across clustering algorithms and Average optimal number of clusters as a function of transcript family size

Figure 3: **(Top) Distribution of silhouette scores across clustering algorithms.** Boxplots show the distribution of best silhouette scores obtained for each transcript family using k-means+euclidean, k-medoids+cosine, and k-medoids+euclidean. The horizontal dashed line indicates the silhouette cutoff (0.3) used to determine whether a transcript family can be meaningfully clustered. **(Bottom) Average optimal number of clusters as a function of transcript family size.** The average best number of clusters k , selected using silhouette analysis, is shown for transcript families of varying sizes under different clustering configurations. The results indicate that the optimal number of clusters is largely independent of transcript family size and is stable across clustering methods.

S1-Text1 : Global behavior across the number of clusters

To determine the optimal k , we computed the Silhouette score across this range and identified local maxima. The Silhouette score quantifies how well a clustering separates data points, ranging from -1 to 1 . Higher values indicate that points are well-matched to their own cluster, values near 0 imply ambiguous assignments near boundaries, and negative values indicate misclassification. We established a cutoff of 0.3 to determine if a transcript family could be meaningfully clustered. All families in our dataset exceeded this threshold, as shown in Supplementary Figure **[S1-Figure1(Top)]**. From the identified local maxima, we selected the smallest k within the interval $[S_{best} - \epsilon, S_{best}]$ (where $\epsilon = 0.02$ and S_{best} is the highest local maximum) to avoid unnecessarily large cluster counts. Consequently, the chosen k represents the estimated number of ortholog trees that constitute the full transcript tree for a given family.

Supplementary Figure **[S1-Figure3(bottom)]** displays the average optimal k relative to transcript family size for all three configurations. We observed that the optimal k is largely independent of transcript family size and assumes to primarily capture an underlying functional signal. Notably, approximately 90% of families (specifically those with fewer than 35 transcripts) stabilized at a best $k = 2$, regardless of the clustering configuration. This suggests that fixing $k = 2$ allows us to infer a broad set of relationships, though potentially at the cost of decreased sensitivity compared to the *tsm-method*.

Several hypotheses may explain this trend, including the influence of family size on clustering resolution and the possibility that small transcript families naturally exhibit limited isoortholog diversity. Furthermore, these small families are not devoid of complexity; approximately 30% of them exhibit a paralogy ratio greater than 0.6 (defined as the number of gene paralog pairs divided by the total number of gene pairs), indicating a non-negligible presence of para-isoorthologous transcripts. This observation supports the assumption that gene paralogs can potentially retain isoforms with similar functions.